

**Extension of Michael's Reaction. Part I.—Action
of Urethane on Esters of Unsaturated Acids.
Part II.—Action of Urethane on Carb-
imides and Thiocarbimides.**

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Part I.

Condensations between sodium derivatives of acetoacetic ester and malonic ester have been studied extensively by a large number of workers (Michael, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1887, 35, 351; 1891, 43, 395; 1892, 45, 55; 1894, 49, 20; Auwers, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 317, 2887; 1893, 26, 364; 1895, 28, 263, 1131; *Annalen*, 1896, 292, 147; Vorländer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2053; *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 253; Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 73, 727, 1006; Hope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 892; Ingold, Shoppee and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1477; Ingold and Shoppee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1912).

The condensation of urethane which, it is well known, readily forms sodium derivative does not appear to have been studied on the line of Michael's condensation. The only work on record appears to be that of Diels and Heintzel (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 297) who got ethyl cinnamoylcarbamate $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ by the direct action of ethyl carbamate on cinnamic ester. The present investigation was undertaken with two objects in view, firstly, to see whether sodium derivative of urethane lends itself like the sodium derivatives of acetoacetic and malonic esters to ordinary Michael's condensation and secondly to utilise the addition compounds, if so formed, for the preparation of amino-acids, thus—

The existing methods for the preparation of amino-acids by the direct addition of ammonia and hydroxylamine to unsaturated acids are very tedious (*cf.* Curtius, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1904, 70, 204; Engel, *Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 1805). Sodium ethylcarbamate in etheral suspension has now been found to react with ethyl cinnamate to give an addition compound which, on treatment with acid, yields a substance possessing the empirical formula, $C_{14}H_{19}O_4N$ which may possess either of the following two structures.

It was expected that the urethanylphenylpropionic ester so formed, on hydrolysis, would give aminophenylpropionic acid as urethane gives ammonia, carbon dioxide and alcohol. But on hydrolysis (*vide* Experimental) it gets decomposed into urethane and cinnamic acid and this suggests that the urethenyl group was attached to the β -carbon atom of the phenylpropionic ester. Decomposition of β -amino- and β -hydroxy-acids into ammonia or water and unsaturated acids is well known. Similar condensations have also been tried with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrocinnamic esters and in each case the corresponding β -urethanyl compounds (II, III and IV) have been obtained. With the hope of getting the carbethoxy derivative of aspartic ester the action of urethane in presence of sodium was tried upon fumaric ester.

Due to the very poor yield of compound (V) which did not respond to any test for unsaturation, the isolation of aspartic acid from it by hydrolysis could not be successfully effected, though an attempt was made in that direction. Citraconic ester similarly adds up urethane to yield urethanylmethyl succinic ester (VI).

By analogy, the action of acetamide, propionamide, benzamide and phthalamide, all of which form sodium derivatives, was similarly studied upon cinnamic ester with the result that both acetamide and propionamide were found to react with the ester yielding cinnamic acid amide. The reaction evidently takes the following course.

Benzamide and phthalamide do not react at all.

Part II.

Seeing that urethane adds up to the double bond of unsaturated acid esters, it was thought worth-while to study the action of urethane upon unsaturated compounds like isocyanates and thiocarbimides. The action of acetoacetic and malonic esters upon thiocarbimides has been studied by Worrall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1055; 1922, **44**, 1551; 1923, **45**, 3092; 1924, **46**, 2832; 1928, **50**, 1456).

Phenylisocyanate reacts readily with urethane to yield sodium derivative of carbethoxyphenylurea, thus:

Phenylthiocarbimide reacts with urethane to give a compound (m.p. 248°) and possessing the composition $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_3\text{S}_2$ (Found: N, 13.57; S, 20.14 per cent.) whereas the expected carbethoxyphenylthiourea (m.p. 130°, Doran, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, **69**, 326) requires N, 12.50 and S, 14.22 per cent. Evidently the reaction takes a different course. Mustard oils are well known to react with thiocarbimides and dithiocarbazine acids and their derivatives to form ring-closed compounds (Busch and Wolpert, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 304). By analogy with this sort of behaviour of mustard oils, the formation of the compound (m.p. 248°) can be explained on the assumption that the expected carbethoxyphenylthiourea, as soon as it is formed, reacts with

another molecule of mustard oil to yield a triazine compound, thus:

The alternative formula (IXa) has been rejected because of the fact that from the methylthiol-derivative of the compound one atom of sulphur can be removed as mercuric sulphide, on treatment with red oxide of mercury in alcoholic solution—which shows that the second sulphur atom is not present in the molecule as a member of the ring (as in IXa) but it is present in the thioketonic form (as in IX) (*vide* Busch, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 304; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1502). That the reaction actually takes the course as indicated above has been proved by condensing carbethoxyphenylthiourea (prepared by Doran's method, *loc. cit.*) with phenyl mustard oil when a compound identical with (IX) is obtained. Similar compounds (X, XI, and XII) have been obtained with *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, and 1:3:4-xylyl mustard oils and they have all been shown to be identical with compounds prepared from the corresponding carbethoxythioureas prepared by Doran's method (*loc. cit.*) and mustard oils. This method of condensing mustard oils with carbethoxythioureas has been utilised for the preparation of isomeric triazine compounds (type IX) *e.g.*, carbethoxyphenylthiourea and *o*-tolyl mustard oil give a compound different from but isomeric with that obtained from carbethoxy-*o*-tolylthiourea and phenyl mustard oil. Compounds (XVII, XVIII, XIX, XX) have been similarly obtained by condensing carbethoxy derivatives of *p*-tolylthiourea with phenyl, *o*-tolyl and allyl mustard oils and carbethoxy-*o*-tolylthiourea with allyl mustard oil.

(XVII)

(XVIII)

(XIX)

(XX)

The behaviour of allyl mustard oil in its reaction with urethane appears to be different from that observed with the aromatic mustard oils described above—in so far as it gives the corresponding carbethoxythiourea which when separately treated with another molecule of allyl mustard oil gives the diallyl substituted triazine compound. It is to be mentioned here that in the case of the aromatic mustard oils the triazine compounds are formed irrespective of the quantity of mustard oils taken. Carbethoxyphenylurea $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, however, has been found to possess no capacity for reacting further with mustard oils and isocyanates to yield triazine compounds as the corresponding carbethoxythioureas always do.

The preparation of thiocarbonyldiurethane, $\text{CS}(\text{NHCO}_2\text{Et})_2$ (XXI) has now been attempted by condensing carbethoxythiocarbimide with urethane in presence of sodium and dry ether. The expected sodium derivative of thiocarbonyldiurethane on acidification, was found to decompose into carbon dioxide, alcohol and other products. It, however, gives a stable copper derivative which has been analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Urethanylphenylpropionic Ester (I).—Sodium (1.2 g.) was put into a solution of urethane (4.5 g.) in absolute ether (150 c.c.). Hydrogen began to evolve profusely for about 2 hours and a white precipitate (sodium derivative of urethane) came down. To this ethyl cinnamate (8.8 g.) was then added and the reaction mixture allowed to stand overnight. Next morning the precipitate was filtered, washed with ether and absolute alcohol and then dissolved in water. The aqueous solution, on being treated with dilute hydrochloric acid, gave a white precipitate which crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 70° . It does not decolourise bromine water. (Found: N, 4.83. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires N, 5.28 per cent.).

*β -Urethanyl-*o*-nitrophenylpropionic Ester (II).*—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of compound (I). The compound was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 210° . (Found: N, 8.81. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

*β -Urethanyl-*m*-nitrophenylpropionic Ester (III).*—It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 195° . (Found: N, 8.74. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

β -Urethanyl-p-nitrophenylpropionic Ester (IV).—The substance was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. above 280°. (Found: N, 8.79. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of Compound (I).—The compound (I) was heated with 5 per cent. caustic potash solution under reflux on the water-bath for about an hour. The clear colourless solution, when cold, was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a shining colourless crystalline mass came down. It was found to melt at 132-133° after crystallisation from hot water and was identified to be cinnamic acid by taking the mixed melting point with a genuine sample. The hydrolysis can also be effected with 2N-hydrochloric acid.

Action of Urethane on Methyl Fumarate: Formation of N-Carbothoxyaspartic Ester (V).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (I). The copper derivative was obtained by adding a concentrated solution of copper acetate and this gave the free urethanyl compound on acidification and extraction with ether. The solid obtained from the ethereal extract on evaporation crystallised from boiling water, m.p. 130° (shrinks at 110°). (Found: N, 5.54. $C_9H_{15}O_6N$ requires N, 6.01 per cent.). The yield of this substance was too poor to allow hydrolysis being studied.

Urethanylmethylsuccinic Ester (VI).—Citraconic ester (9.3 g.) was added to an ethereal suspension of sodiourethane prepared from urethane (4.5 g.) and sodium (1.2 g.) and the reaction mixture allowed to stand overnight. Next morning, a fine yellow solid was obtained which after filtration and washing with dry ether was found to get coloured on exposure to air. So it was quickly dissolved in water and the copper derivative was obtained as a greenish mass by adding a concentrated solution of copper acetate. The copper derivative, however, seemed to be quite stable. The free urethanyl compound was generated from its copper derivative by shaking an ethereal suspension of the latter with dilute sulphuric acid. The ethereal layer after being dehydrated over anhydrous magnesium sulphate was evaporated to dryness. The heavy brownish liquid thus obtained showed no tendency towards solidification even when kept in vacuum for a long time. (Found: N, 4.62. $C_{12}H_{21}O_6N$ requires N, 5.09 per cent.).

Action of Urethane on Mesaconic Ester: Formation of Urethanylmethylsuccinic Ester (VIa).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (VI). The brownish red heavy liquid obtained from the copper derivative on acidification

could not be solidified even on long standing in vacuum over sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 4.64. $C_{12}H_{21}O_6N$ requires N, 5.09 per cent.).

Action of Acetamide on Cinnamic Ester: Formation of Cinnamamide (VII).—Sodium (1.2 g.) was gradually added to a solution of acetamide (3 g.) in absolute ether (120 c.c.). The evolution of hydrogen ceased after about two hours when the sodium derivative of acetamide separated as a white precipitate. The mixture after the addition of ethyl cinnamate (9 g.) was allowed to stand overnight. Next morning the separated orange-yellow solid was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid mixed with some tarry matter was obtained. On boiling with water the solid went into solution leaving behind the tarry matter and the filtrate after treatment with animal charcoal and concentration yielded white shining plates, m.p. 142-143°. It is readily soluble in alcohol, acetic acid but sparingly so in benzene. It is soluble in strong hydrochloric acid but not in alkali. (Found: N, 9.26. C_9H_9ON requires N, 9.52 per cent.). The compound decolourises bromine water and the isolated bromo-derivative melts at 200° (decomp.).

The action of propionamide on cinnamic ester was similarly tried and the resulting compound (m.p. 142-143°) was proved to be cinnamamide by taking the mixed melting point with the product obtained in the preceding experiment as also by hydrolysing it with 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution when cinnamic acid was obtained.

Carbethoxyphenylcarbamide (VIII).—Phenylisocyanate (6 g.) was added to an ethereal suspension of sodiourethane obtained from sodium (1.2 g.) and urethane (4.5 g.). The reaction at once started and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The white precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a colourless precipitate came down which crystallised from alcohol in beautiful, colourless, plates, m.p. 106-107°. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.46 per cent.).

1:5-Diphenyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (IX).—Phenyl mustard oil (7 g.) was added to an ethereal suspension of sodiourethane obtained from sodium (1.2 g.) and urethane (4.5 g.), and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The yellow precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated semi-solid mass was purified by dissolving it in ether and precipitating by means of petroleum ether and finally crystallising from methyl alcohol in beautiful, yellow, rectan-

gular prisms, m.p. 249°. (Found: N, 18·57; S, 20·14. $C_{15}H_{11}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 18·41; S, 20·44 per cent.). It is soluble in cold alkali from which it is precipitated by acids. It is decomposed on boiling with dilute alkali.

The *monomethyl* derivative was obtained by dissolving compound (IX) in the minimum quantity of caustic soda solution and boiling the solution with the requisite quantity of methyl iodide in presence of alcohol for about 15 minutes when colourless crystals came out. These were recrystallised from alcohol in shining, hexagonal prisms, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 12·53. $C_{16}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·84 per cent.).

The *benzoyl* derivative was obtained by Schotten-Baumann process and was crystallised from alcohol in shining colourless prisms, m.p. 158—159°. The *bromo-derivative* was obtained by dissolving the compound (IX) in glacial acetic acid and adding bromine water. The precipitate was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 200° (after shrinking and softening at 140°).

Action of Red Oxide of Mercury on the above Methyl Derivative: Formation of 1:5-Diphenyl-2-methylthiol-4:6-diketoheptahydro-1:3:5-triazine.—The monomethyl derivative of compound (IX) in alcoholic solution was boiled with an excess of mercuric oxide which turned black due to its conversion into mercuric sulphide. The alcoholic filtrate on evaporation to dryness left a white solid which crystallised from alcohol in shining, colourless plates, m. p. 195°. (Found: N, 13·18. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2SN_3$ requires N, 13·50 per cent.).

1:5-Di-o-tolyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketoheptahydro-1:3:5-triazine (X).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (IX). It was crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellow, rectangular prisms, m. p. 280°. It is soluble in cold alkali from which it is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 12·00; S, 18·50; C, 59·41; H, 4·88. $C_{17}H_{15}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·31; S, 18·76; C, 59·82; H, 4·39 per cent.).

1:5-Di-m-tolyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketoheptahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XI).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the phenyl and *o*-tolyl compounds. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellow, rectangular prisms, m.p. 237° (after shrinking at 226°). It is soluble in cold alkali from which is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 12·12. $C_{17}H_{15}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·31 per cent.).

1:5-Dizylyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohezahydro-1:3:5-triasine (XII).— was prepared similarly from sodiourethane and 1:3:4-xylyl mustard oil and, after effecting the precipitation with petrol from ethereal solution, was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 223-225°. It is soluble in cold alkali from which it is precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 10·94. $C_{19}H_{19}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 11·38 per cent.).

3-Carbethoxy-1-allylthiourea, $C_3H_5NH\cdot CS\cdot NH\cdot CO_2Et$ (XIII).— Molecular proportions of sodiourethane and allyl mustard oil were allowed to stand in presence of dry ether for 24 hours. The precipitated sodium derivative after filtration and washing was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The semi-solid white mass that came down was purified by dissolving it in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was finally crystallised from alcohol in colourless, rectangular plates, m. p. 57°. (Found: N, 15·06 ; S, 16·61. $C_7H_{12}O_2SN_2$ requires N, 14·89 ; S, 17·02 per cent.).

1:5-Diallyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohezahydro-1:3:5-triasine (XIV).— Sodium (1·2 g.) was dissolved in a solution of carbethoxyallylthiocarbamide (9·4 g.) dissolved in 156 c.c. of absolute ether. Hydrogen began to evolve profusely for about two hours during which period the sodium derivative went on being gradually deposited as a white precipitate. The reaction mixture, after the addition of allyl mustard oil (10 g.) to it, was allowed to stand overnight. Next morning the reaction mixture was found to be free from any smell of allyl mustard oil and the precipitate that had separated out was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was purified by dissolving it in ether and shaking with sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline solution on being acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded a precipitate which crystallised readily from alcohol, m. p. 133°. (Found: N, 17·14. $C_9H_{11}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 17·42 per cent.).

1:5-Diphenyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohezahydro-1:3:5-triasine (IX).— Sodium (1 g.) was added to a solution of carbethoxyphenylthiocarbamide (10 g.) in dry ether (120 c.c.). After about two hours, when all the sodium has reacted, phenyl mustard oil (6 g.) was added and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The aqueous solution of the separated solid on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid yielded a yellow precipitate which was dissolved in ether and shaken with a solution of sodium carbonate. The alkaline solution, on acidification gave a precipitate which crystallised readily from methyl

alcohol in beautiful, yellow, rectangular prisms, m. p. 248°. (Found N, 13·12. $C_{13}H_{11}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 13·41 per cent.). The identity of this compound with (IX) was confirmed by taking a mixed melting point.

Action of Carbethoxyphenylthiourea upon o-Tolyl Mustard Oil : Formation of 1-Phenyl-5-o-tolyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XV).—The method of preparation and purification was the same as in the case of the compound (IX). The compound was crystallised from methyl alcohol in rectangular prisms, m. p. 244°-245°. It gives insoluble mercury and lead salts with mercuric chloride and lead acetate solutions respectively. (Found: N, 12·67. $C_{16}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·84 per cent.). The benzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless, shining prisms, m. p. 205°.

Action of Carbethoxy-o-tolylthiocarbamide upon Phenyl Mustard Oil : Formation of 1-o-Tolyl-5-phenyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XVI).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the compound (XV). The yellow precipitate obtained from the sodium carbonate solution crystallised from methyl alcohol in rectangular prisms, m. p. 235°-236°. (Found: N, 12·72. $C_{16}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·84 per cent.). The benzoyl derivative was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 155°.

Action of Carbethoxy-p-tolylthiocarbamide upon Phenyl Mustard Oil : Formation of 1-p-Tolyl-5-phenyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XVII).—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the compound (XV). The yellow precipitate was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 251-252°. (Found: N, 12·61. $C_{16}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·84 per cent.).

Action of Carbethoxy-p-tolylthiocarbamide upon o-Tolyl Mustard Oil : Formation of 1-p-Tolyl-5-o-tolyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XVIII).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (XV). It was obtained in yellow rectangular prisms from methyl alcohol, m. p. 224°. (Found: N, 12·09. $C_{17}H_{15}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 12·31 per cent.).

Action of Carbethoxy-p-tolylthiocarbamide upon Allyl Mustard Oil : Formation of 1-p-Tolyl-5-allyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XIX).—The substance was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 145°, (Found: N, 14·12. $C_{13}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 14·48 per cent.)

Action of Carbethoxy-o-tolylthiocarbamide upon Allyl Mustard Oil: Formation of 1-o-Tolyl-5-allyl-2:6-dithion-4-ketohexahydro-1:3:5-triazine (XX).—It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 136-137°. (Found: N, 14·21. $C_{13}H_{13}OS_2N_3$ requires N, 14·43 per cent.).

Thiocarbonyl diurethane (XXI).—Carbethoxythiocarbimide (6·6 g.) prepared according to the method of Doran, (*loc.cit.*) and dissolved in toluene was added to a toluene suspension of sodiourethane obtained from sodium (1·2 g.) and urethane (4·5 g.) and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. Next morning the precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in an ice-cold bath when carbon dioxide began to evolve profusely and a reddish-brown tarry matter was obtained. The copper derivative was, however, obtained by adding a concentrated solution of copper acetate to the aqueous solution of the sodium derivative and a brownish-white precipitate was obtained, which was washed with alcohol, water and dried. (Found: N, 11·14. $(C_7H_{11}O_4SN_2)_2Cu$ requires N, 11·16 per cent.). The copper derivative also decomposes on the addition of acids.

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